

The Influence of Basic Disaster Management Training on Competencies in The Human Resources Development Agency of North Sumatra Province

Yurlinda¹, Kiki Farida Ferine²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*Correspondence Email: yurlinda74@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of Basic Training on Employee Competency of North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency employees. This research was carried out at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 107 employees of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The sampling technique in this research uses saturated samples so that the entire population will be a sample of 107 people. The research results show that Basic Training has a positive but not significant influence on Employee Competency as indicated by the T-Statistic value of $2.784 > 1.659$ and the P Value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that improvements in Basic Training will be able to increase the Competency of Employees of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The adjusted R Square value is 0.214 or 21.40%, which means that basic training has a low influence on employee competency, while the remaining 78.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Keywords: Basic Training; Competence

INTRODUCTION

The state apparatus, which is an element of human resources for government agencies, has a role that determines the success of government administration and development. To form good government officials in order to increase competence, one effort is through the implementation of education and training (training). Training is a necessity for a bureaucratic organization and is part of human resource development as well as one of the solutions to solving problems that occur in an organization.

Good employee competency is something that organizations desire. The more disciplined employees in a company, the company's overall competency or productivity will increase (Juliyanti & Onsardi, 2020). Employee competency is an important factor in an organization because with good competency an organization is on its way to success. High employee competency will help the organization achieve strategic goals. Factors that influence competency according to Siagian in (Riyani, 2021) Employee competency is influenced by several factors, namely competency, employee training, work environment, work culture, leadership, motivation, discipline and job satisfaction. Meanwhile, the factors that influence competency are motivation, job satisfaction, stress level, work conditions, compensation system, and job design (Handoko, 2014).

Training is a process of teaching certain knowledge and skills as well as attitudes so that employees become more skilled and able to carry out their responsibilities better, in accordance with standards (Mangkunegara, 2016). In view of this, the North Sumatra Province Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDM) realizes that human resource

management is a very important factor in the activities of disaster management officers and the agency is well aware that they need qualified officers to support the functions of BPSDM, for this reason Many aspects are needed, one of which is Human Resources who have the ability and skills to carry out disaster management. Because disasters can occur at any time and anywhere, it is important for BPSDM to prepare important elements in disaster management. National disaster data for 2016 shows that the intensity of disaster events is very high. This fact indicates that the intensity of disasters in Indonesia in general is still high.

Regarding training, BPSDM North Sumatra continues to carry out training for its employees, but not frequently. This is one of the causes of decreasing employee competence. The infrequent training that is carried out means that a small number of employees are unable to use the equipment properly, and there are also employees who consider training to be a waste of budget. Because usually that's the only training material that is carried out. This results in the achievement of the competencies obtained not being optimal. Apart from training, competency is also an important thing for employees to have. Competence is also a determining factor in increasing competence.

Training is an effort to transfer skills and knowledge to training participants in such a way that participants receive and carry out training while carrying out work (Wahyuningsih, 2019). Training is carried out because technology is increasingly developing so that training is provided to employees in the hope that employees can be more competitive in carrying out their obligations (Tjiptono, 2016).

According to (Sari, 2018) training is all efforts to provide, obtain, improve and maintain work skills, product output, attitudes and ethics at certain levels of abilities and skills, in accordance with the standards and qualifications of positions and jobs. A process for obtaining and improving one's Basic Training and increasing employee productivity. Training is part of the process of increasing human capital capital that can support organizational goals (Wibowo et al., 2019).

According to (Wahyuningsih, 2019) there are 5 indicators in training, namely: Starting

1. Training Objectives

Training objectives must be realistic and can be delivered in such a way that training is carried out to develop work skills so that participants can increase awareness of the work that participants must do.

2. Material

In the form of work management, essays, work correspondence, work psychology, work discipline and ethics, as well as work reporting, teaching materials can be used.

3. Method used

In training, the method used is teaching with a participatory approach such as group discussions, seminars, exercises, practice (demonstrations) and games, educational events, tests, group work visits and studies (comparative studies).

4. Participant Qualifications

Participants are employees who have passed the qualification requirements, such as permanent employees and employees with recommendations from leaders.

5. Coach qualifications

Trainers/providers of training to participants must meet qualification requirements such as: having skills related to the training material, being able to generate inspiration and motivation in participants and using participatory methods.

Competency is the ability to carry out or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitudes required by the job (Wibowo, 2016). Employee competency is a very important thing to pay attention to because it is related to knowledge, skills and work attitudes that are in accordance with established standards (Sutrisno, 2017). For this reason, employees need to improve their quality and abilities by participating in various trainings in order to gain knowledge and insight so they can carry out their duties and responsibilities in carrying out their work.

Competency variable indicators according to Gordon's theory in (Sutrisno, 2017) state that employee competency indicators consist of:

- 1) Knowledge (Knowledge)
- 2) Understanding (Understanding)
- 3) Abilities/Skills (Skills)
- 4) Value (Value)
- 5) Attitude (Attitude)
- 6) Interests

The aim of this research is to analyze and determine the influence of Basic Training on Competency in regional officials in North Sumatra Province. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency. The time this research was carried out was from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency, totaling 107 people.

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 107 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Competency

X = Basic Training

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Basic Training (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee competency (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Basic Training	107	1.83	5.00	3.8489	,82083
Competence	107	1.60	5.00	3.8206	,76328
Valid N (listwise)	107				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents rated the Basic Training and Competency of employees at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency as above average, with mean values of 3,848 and 3,820 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.8208 for Basic Training and 0.7632 for Employee Competency), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of both variables. these variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Basic Training Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
DIK1	0.613 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
DIK2	0.682 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
DIK3	0.629 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
DIK4	0.722 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
DIK5	0.685 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the Basic Education and Training variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.190 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Basic Education and Training variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Employee Competency Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KOM1	0.638 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM2	0.687 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM3	0.714 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM4	0.619 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM5	0.720 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KOM6	0.680 > 0.190	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that all indicators on the employee competency variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.190 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee competency variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2018).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Basic Training	0.687	5
Employee Competency	0.760	6

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the Basic Training and Employee Competency variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	23,548	,356		9,964	,000
Basic Training	,671	,090	,076	2,784	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Competence

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 23.548 + 0.671X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 23.548 means that if there is no Basic Training, then there is an employee competency of 23.548 points. The Basic

Training regression coefficient is 0.671, meaning that Basic Training influences an increase in employee competency by 0.671 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,376a	,141	,214	,76467

a. Predictors: (Constant), Basic Training

The test results in table 7 obtained an Adjusted R Square value of 0.214 or 21.40%, which means that Basic Training has a low category influence on employee competency while the remaining 78.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of Basic Training on employee competency at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency

Ha: There is an influence of Basic Training on employee competency at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23,548	,356	9,964	,000
	Basic Training	,671	,090	,076	2,784

a. Dependent Variable: Competence

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is 2.784 > t table 1.659, with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between Basic Education and Training on employee competency at the Resource Development Agency. North Sumatra Human Resources.

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Basic Training on the Competency of Employees of the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency, the existence of Training can improve the skills and abilities of employees to carry out work. Training also has an effect in transferring skills and knowledge to training participants in such a way that participants receive and carry out training while carrying out work (Fathoni, 2015).

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the data analysis of the research results and discussion described above, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between Basic Training on employee competency at the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency as evidenced by the calculated t value of $2.784 > t_{table} 1,659$, with a significance value $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that if basic training is improved, employee competency will tend to increase. If training is improved, the competency of North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency employees will also increase.

The results of the termination coefficient test show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.214 or 21.40%, which means that Basic Training has a low category influence on employee competency while the remaining 78.60% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be given to the North Sumatra Human Resources Development Agency are as follows:

1. Strengthen and develop the training program with several concrete steps, such as conducting regular evaluations and modernizing basic training materials to make them more relevant and effective.
2. Focus on improving employee performance and recognition. Developing a performance measurement system that is integrated with training results and providing rewards and incentives for employees who demonstrate increased competence and performance is an important step. In addition, involving employees in planning and developing training programs and creating discussion forums to obtain input will improve the quality of training programs.

REFERENCES

- Ghozali, I. (2018). *Multivariate Analysis Application with the IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
- Handoko, TH (2014). *Personnel and Human Resources Management (2nd ed.)*. BFFE Yogyakarta.

- Juliyanti, B., & Onsardi. (2020). The Influence of Work Discipline and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at the Bengkulu City Regional Drinking Water Company (PDAM). *Journal of Human Capital Management and Business (JMMIB)*, 1, 183–191. <https://jurnal.imsi.or.id/index.php/jmmib/article/view/20>
- Kuncoro, M., & Hardani, W. (2013). *Research Methods for Business and Economics How to Research and Write a Thesis?* (4th ed.). Erlangga.
- Mangkunegara, AP (2016). *Corporate Human Resources Management* (Print 13). Rosdakarya Teenager.
- Riyani, WN (2021). The Influence of Work Discipline, Motivation and Competence on PT Employee Performance. Perkebunan Nusantara VII South Sumatra Liaison Office. In Sriwijaya University.
- Sari, P. Eka. (2018). The Influence of Training and Work Discipline on Employees of PT Bank Aceh Medan. *Journal of Management and Finance*, 7(1), 100–109. <https://doi.org/10.33059/jmk.v7i1.750>
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Combination Research Methods (Mixed Methods)*. Alfabeta.
- Sutrisno, E. (2017). *Human Resource Management* (9th ed.). Kencana.
- Tjiptono, F. (2016). *Service, Quality and Satisfaction 4*. Andi Publisher.
- Wahyuningsih, S. (2019). The Effect of Training in Increasing Employee Work Productivity. *Journal News Edition*, 60(April), 91–96.
- Wibowo. (2016). *Performance Management* (4th ed.). Rajawali Press.
- Wibowo, AE, Ratnawati, T., & Sardjono, S. (2019). The Influence of Parent's Socio-Economic Status, Financial Governance, Financial Learning in Higher Education on Financial Literacy, Lifestyle and Human Capital Investment of Economics and Business Students in Batam City Indonesia. *Journal of Archives of Business Research*, 7(6), 33–43.